

LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE THROUGH LISTENING

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Annotation: The main goal of learning a foreign language is the formation and improvement of communicative competence. There are two ways of communication in language learning: oral (listening and speaking) and written (reading and writing). In this article, we will focus on listening as an integral part of foreign language learning. Listening competence is one of the most relevant topics in the modern methodology of teaching a foreign language, because it is impossible to communicate without listening.

Key words: listening, speaking, semantic perception, abstraction, audio tasks, learning, communicative competence

Language is the most important means of communication, without which the existence and development of human society is impossible. The changes taking place today in social relations, means of communication (the use of new information technologies) require increasing the communicative competence of students, improving their philological training. The main purpose of the English language is to form communicative competence, the ability and readiness to carry out foreign language interpersonal and intercultural communication with native speakers. It is known that language is a means of communication in two forms: oral (listening and speaking) and written (reading and writing). It is these four types of speech activity that are present in the teacher's field of vision. Let us dwell on listening as an integral part of teaching English. Listening at the initial stage of learning is one of the most relevant topics in the modern methodology of teaching

English, since speech communication is impossible without listening.

Listening (understanding of speech perceived by ear) is the basis of communication, mastering communication begins with it. Listening can be a separate type of communicative activity with its own motive, reflecting the needs of a person or the nature of his activity. For example, when watching a movie, TV show, using the Internet, listening to a radio show. Sufficient mastery of listening as a type of speech activity not only allows, but also stimulates independent viewing of films and TV shows in English.

The main mental processes that are involved in listening are the following: memory, imagination, perception and thinking. Thus, by activating these features of the human psyche, we simultaneously develop them, which is a fundamental factor in the comprehensive development of the individual. And, therefore, listening can be considered an integral part of developmental learning.

The semantic perception of speech by ear affects such concepts as analysis, comparison, abstraction, concretization, and others. Characterizing the essence of perception (auditory and visual), it is necessary to strictly distinguish between two concepts: perception and recognition. The value of inner speech for understanding is very great, it makes it possible to perceive speech messages, predict and generalize. At the initial stage of learning, inner speech proceeds especially intensively, and it can be considered as the main and necessary component of auditory perception. Speaking and listening are two interrelated aspects of oral speech. Listening is not only the reception of a message, but also the preparation in inner speech of a response to what is heard. Listening is not only a goal, but also a means of learning. It makes it possible to master the sound side of the studied language, its phonemic composition and intonation: rhythm, stress, melody. Through listening at the initial stage, the lexical side of the language and its grammatical structure are mastered.

In the process of mastering listening comprehension in English, students encounter a number of linguistic difficulties: phonetic, lexical, grammatical. In the

first grade, it is especially difficult, for example, to distinguish sounds by ear: [æ - e], [o: - ə], [e - i], [i: - i]. Knowing this, the teacher uses exercises that remove such difficulties. It teaches students to distinguish sounds in isolation and in combinations, to hear the difference in the pronunciation of [s], [z], [b] and [p], to hear longitude and brevity, to recognize the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of sounds, rhythm, stress and their meaningful function.

The first and most necessary condition for the formation of students' understanding of English speech is the teacher conducting a lesson in English. Hence, great demands are placed on the speech of the teacher.

Listening is used as a means of introducing students to new language or speech material. To organize an acquaintance with new material means to show students the meaning, form and use of it. So, when getting acquainted with a new vocabulary, in order to master the form, it is necessary to repeatedly perceive it by students; to understand the meaning, you can use a non-translating way of revealing the meaning and only, if necessary, a translation; situations are needed to illustrate the use of a new word. It is much easier to do this if the student feels the need to express his thoughts and perceive oral material, whether it be audio material or an oral statement by a teacher or classmate.

In addition to familiarization, listening is also used in organizing the training of students in mastering the material.

The volume of a voice message depends on many factors and is not a stable value. You can only talk about the minimum or maximum size of the audio text and determine it not by the number of words or sentences, but by the duration of the sound. Such a measurement is convenient for planning classes, for the correct distribution of time for various types of speech activities.

An interesting feature of learning when using audio tools is the fact that replicas, phrases of speech etiquette in different listening situations make a great impression on students and are assimilated involuntarily, more easily consolidated and remain in memory in the right intonation and fast pace of speech. The success

of listening depends, on the one hand, on the listener himself (on the degree of development of speech hearing, memory, on his attention, interest), on the other hand, on the conditions of perception (number and form of presentation, duration of sound) and, finally, on linguistic features - linguistic and structural-compositional complexities of speech messages and their correspondence to the speech experience and knowledge of students.

As mentioned above, listening is the basis of communication, mastering oral communication begins with it. Possession of such a type of speech activity as listening allows a person to understand what is being told to him and adequately respond to what is said, helps to correctly state his answer to the opponent, which is the basis of dialogical speech. In this case, listening teaches the culture of speech: listen to the interlocutor carefully and always listen to the end, which is important not only when speaking in English, but also in your native language. At the present stage, listening is included in all exams for the level of English proficiency, representing international certificates IELTS, TOEFL, CEFR and others.

REFERENCES

1. Р.Шомуродова, Х. У. Сайдуллаева «Некоторые особенности научно- технического перевода» Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук. Москва 2019 (78-83)
2. З.Р.Шомуродова «Основное содержание перевода научной и технической литературы» Вопросы науки и образования Москва 2020/11 (70-74)
3. Z.R.Shomurodova «Teaching English for specific purpose to improve students` level» Xorazm Mamun Akademiyasi axborotnomasi Khiva 2020/7 (139-137)
4. Татаринев В.А. Методология научного перевода. – М.: Московский Лицей, 2007. – 526 с.
5. Ци Ванчжи. Термины в языке газеты: автореф. дис. ... канд.

филол. наук. – М., 2006. – 20 с.

6. M.N.Mirzaeva Technology forming professional competence of students of technical university in the lessons of foreign languages// Научные горизонты, 2019

7. M.N.Mirzaeva Formation of concept and technologies of cultural competence at students of technical universities//Theoretical & Applied Science, 2020

8. M.N.Mirzayeva, S. Xasanov, A. Goziyev Communicative competence as a component of the professional competence of a technical specialist//Актуальные вопросы современной науки, 2021

9. M.H.Мирзаева The acquisition of a foreign language//Молодой ученый, 2017

10. I.A.Sharipova Efficiency of interactive methods of teaching a professionally-oriented English language for students of a technical university.// Theoretical & Applied Science, 2019

11. I.A.Sharipova Efficiency of interactive methods of teaching a professionally-oriented English language for students of a technical university.// Theoretical & Applied Science, 2019

